

THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN BANKING AND FINANCIAL PYRAMID

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Annotation: A banking and financial institution is mainly engaged in the collection of temporarily vacant funds, lending to enterprises and those in need of money in general, cashless settlements, issuance of money and various securities, gold and foreign exchange transactions. and other activities. Typically, financial pyramids are registered as commercial organizations and are supposed to attract "investment" to finance a particular project. At the same time, investors are promised impossible things, such as large returns in the long run. This article discusses the opinions and considerations about the difference between a banking and a financial pyramid.

Keywords: bank, financial pyramid, credit, money, investment, people.

In fact, the organization does not produce any value and survives on the fees paid by new members. In this sense, a financial pyramid is different from a real business entity. Lack of production and huge promises lead to the inevitable collapse of the financial pyramid. The desire of people to get rich quick and make easy money pours water into the mill of the organizers of the financial pyramid. The organizers initially pay the participants the promised money in order to gain trust and gain a reputation among the people. In this way, rumors that the financial pyramid actually paid the promised money spread among relatives and acquaintances, and the "business" of the organizers flourished.

But as the number of participants grows, it will be impossible to keep their promises. Because as the number of participants in the pyramid grows, so does the amount of money that must be paid each month. In addition, the organizers lose control of incoming cash flow and begin to resort to extravagant purchases: the proceeds will be used to buy expensive apartments, cars, etc., and the cost of these purchases will only increase. According to the analysis, more than 90% of the participants of the pyramid will suffer only from it. Financial pyramids are based on a premeditated plan. His activities go hand in hand with fraud, as he seeks to deceive people. Financial pyramids have also appeared on the Internet in recent years. The activity of such pyramids does not differ significantly from the usual ones.

In short, the financial literacy of the population ensures that everyone in society has a sufficient level of economic knowledge, skills and abilities, as well as a sound approach to economic decision-making, which allows them to ensure

their own well-being. is an indicator of quality. In this context, the press and the media play an important role. The higher the level of financial literacy of the population, the higher the level of stability and prosperity in the individual, the region in which he lives, as well as in the national economy as a whole. The level of development of the country's economy has a positive impact on the level of financial literacy of the population. Of course, this does not mean that there are no problems in this area in developed countries.

References:

1. Huston S.J. Measuring Financial Literacy. The Journal of Consumer Affairs, 2010, vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 296-316.
2. Ulugmurodov D. What is financial literacy? -<http://old.xs.uz/index.php/homepage/zhamiyat/item/10461> -financial literacy-what.
3. I. Turopov. What is financial literacy, and why is it relevant? Bankers.uz

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